

Investigations Impact of Super Fly Ash Plus on Concrete Mechanical Behavior

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Abstract

Pozzolanic materials refer to silica and alumina substances that form strong and permanent compounds with adhesive properties when mixed with water and lime. A significant advantage of using pozzolanic materials is their ability to reduce pollutants during cement production while also preventing surface cracking and enhancing resistance against chemical attacks and sulfates. Fly ash (FA), a common byproduct of coal combustion is a green environmentally-friendly material and pozzolanic additive that can substitute a portion of cement and help reduce pollution associated with cement production. In this paper, we present the findings of an experimental study that utilized a pozzolanic additive called Super Fly Ash Plus (SFAP) as a partial substitute for cement. To achieve this, in conjunction with identification through X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis, the effects of SFAP contents of 0, 5, and 10% were individually assessed on the compressive strength, and modulus of elasticity measurements for a curing age of 28 days. The findings indicate that when the Water/Cement (W/C) and aggregate grading remain constant, increasing the SFAP content enhances the effectiveness of the concrete. Furthermore, SFAP potentiated an increase in the compressive strength, elasticity modulus, and long-term durability of concrete. The most significant improvements were observed at a 10% content.

Keywords: Fly Ash, Elasticity modulus, Green Environmentally-friendly Materials, Green Pozzolan, Compressive Strength

1. Introduction

Concrete is a widely used construction material known for its strength and durability. However, the environmental concerns associated with cement production have led to the exploration of alternative materials to partially replace it, (FA) is an industrial by-product that electricity-generating plants produce. This artificial admixture has been created through the burning of coal or lignite, since the early 20th century [1]. Studies have extensively investigated the effects of fly ash on the properties of concrete. These studies have shown that fly ash particles can fill empty spaces in concrete to create a denser microstructure, leading to increased durability. Additionally, when fly ash reacts with calcium hydroxide in cement, it generates additional cementitious compounds, further improving the concrete's strength and resilience [5,2]. It has been utilized in the production of concrete, and has proven to have advantageous effects on both the fresh and hardened properties of concrete mixtures of supplementary cementitious material due to its pozzolanic properties, specific chemical and mineralogical composition of fly ash can vary depending on the raw material and collection method used properties [1,2,3]. It is possible to replace some of the cement in concrete with fly ash, which can decrease the environmental impact without compromising the performance of the concrete [7]. Several factors affect the mechanical characteristics of concrete upon adding fly ash, including the quantity and type of fly ash utilized, the water-to-cement ratio, the curing surroundings, and the mixture proportions. Furthermore, the effectiveness of fly ash as a supplementary cementitious material is determined by its chemical composition and particle size distribution, and crucial to comprehend how different ratios of fly ash affect the properties of concrete trials for practical applications. Recent laboratory tests revealed that increasing the percentage of (FA) in concrete by more than 30% reduces the compressive and flexural strengths [4,5]. The addition of a significant amount of (FA) to concrete (between 40 and 70%) led to a decrease in its abrasion resistance and impact resistance [7], as well as an increase in its water absorption and an improvement in its resistance to acid [4,6]. Incorporating (FA) in concrete has several advantages, such as improved workability, reduced heat of hydration, and increased long-term strength and durability. However, some difficulties need to be addressed, such as inconsistencies in fly ash properties, slower strength development, and the potential for delayed formation. According to a recent study, adding up to 40% of Class C fly ash in the total cementitious materials has a negligible effect on the abrasion resistance of concrete. However, a slight reduction in abrasion resistance was observed in high-volume fly ash concrete (HVFAC), particularly when the fly ash content exceeded 50%, compared to the reference mix without fly ash [6]. Furthermore, results have indicated that concrete with fly ash can have mechanical properties that are comparable to or even better than those of traditional concrete. The inclusion of fly ash in concrete structures has been found to improve their compressive strength, flexural strength, and resistance to sulfate attack and alkali-silica reactions. This is due to the pozzolanic reaction that occurs between fly ash and cement, leading to the

creation of additional C-S-H gel, which reinforces and protects the concrete. Furthermore, concrete that incorporates fly ash can have lower permeability, which can provide protection against corrosion of the reinforcing steel and thus extend the lifespan of the structure. The presence of fly ash significantly affects the mechanical behavior of concrete mixtures. Achieving the desired properties of concrete requires careful consideration of the selection and dosage of fly ash, as well as optimized mix proportions. Although fly ash has numerous advantages, its use in concrete must be monitored to minimize any potential adverse effects. Overall, the results indicate that fly ash is a valuable supplementary material that effectively enhances the performance and sustainability of concrete.

2. Materials

2.1 Cement classification and XRF test results

This study used Type I- 42.5 cement from the Urmia Cement Factory in Urmia City, West Azerbaijan Province. Comparison and demonstration of the cement outcomes are presented in Table (1), and Figure (3).

Table- 1 XRF analysis of ordinary Portland cement (OPC) CEM type I 42.5 R

Test Parameters	Unit	Test Result OPC Type I 42.5R	EN 197-1 Standard Requirement	Scheme	Amount
SiO ₂	%	20.67		OC-01	688.31
Al ₂ O ₃	%	4.89		OC-01	162.84
Fe ₂ O ₃	%	3.09		OC-01	102.90
CaO	%	63.56		OC-01	2116.55
MgO	%	1.70	Max 5%	OC-01	56.61
SO ₃	%	2.54	Max 3.5%	OC-01	84.58
K ₂ O	%	1.11		OC-01	36.96
Na ₂ O	%	0.23		OC-01	7.66
Loss On Ignition	%	2.08	Max 3.5%	OC-01	69.26
Free Lime	%	1.25		OC-01	41.63
Insoluble Material	%	0.44	Max 0.1%	OC-01	14.65
LSF	%	0.97	Max 5%	OC-01	32.30
C ₃ S	%	56.80		OC-01	1891.44
C ₂ S	%	16.44		OC-01	547.45
C ₃ A	%	7.73		OC-01	257.41
C ₄ AF	%	9.42		OC-01	313.69

2.2 Water

The water used in this experiment is potable water from Urmia City, West Azerbaijan Province, Iran.

2.3 Plasticizer

REONET, produced by Abadgaran Company, is a powerful liquid cloud and water reducer that enhances the performance of concrete by reducing the amount of mixing water needed. It is compatible with all types of Portland cement and can be used simultaneously with micro-silica, fly ash, and other pozzolanic materials. This additive is effective in maintaining the performance of concrete in a paste state and meets industry standards for quality and performance, such as American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) C1017/C1017 M, ASTM C494/C494M TYPE F, EN 934.

Table- 2 Physical and chemical characteristics of Abadgaran, REONET plasticizer

Chemical base	Physical state	Density	Chloride ion
Polycarboxylate	Fluid	1.09±0.05 (g/cm ³)	Does not contain chloride (less than ISIRI 2930)

2.4 Aggregate

According to ASTM C33, aggregate grain size (Sand and Gravel): Gravel constitutes approximately 35 ~ 38% of the total particles, while Sand constitutes about 35% ~ 37% [8]. The aggregate materials are sourced from mines in Urmia, West Azerbaijan Province. Fig. (1,2)

Figure1 - Grain size distribution curve of the fine aggregate (Sand)

Figure- 2 Grain size distribution curve of the coarse aggregate (Gravel)

2.5 Air

Air bubbles are inherently present in concrete compositions, with a mixture of unintentional bubbles that get trapped during the mixing process or due to the irregular shape of aggregates, as well as the deliberate creation of fine air bubbles to achieve specific characteristics. The quantity of air in the concrete typically ranges from 0.2~0.7% [11].

2.6 Fly ash

Fly ash (FA) is a byproduct of coal combustion that possesses remarkable eco-friendly properties and the ability to elevate concrete properties while reducing environmental harm. Its composition of silica and alumina creates robust compounds when blended with lime and water, resulting in enhanced chemical resistance, reduced surface cracking, and superior defense against sulfates. SFAP's potential to enhance concrete performance while reducing environmental impact makes it a highly promising material for various civil engineering applications [3,4,5,6]. The name of FA used in this study is a super flash plus (SFAP), the physical characteristics of which are presented in Table 3 and Figure (4).

Table- 3 SFAP Physical Characteristics

Fly Ash Type	Standards	PH	Color	Density	Specific Surface	Particle Size
				(Kg/m ²)	(mm ² /g)	(micron)
SFAP	ASTM C494-Type G ASTM 618-Class F [9,10]	8~10	Gray	1.6	12~18	0.03~0.12

Figure4 - Super Fly Ash Plus (SFAP)

3. Concrete Mixing Design

3.1.1 Mixing Design Schemes: OC, FA₅, FA₁₀

OC: ordinary concrete without SFAP

FA₅: Concrete containing 5%SFAP

FA₁₀: Concrete containing 10% SFAP

Table- 4 Proportion of concrete materials for 1m³ in Schemes OC, FA₅, and FA₁₀

Scheme	Cement (C)	SFAP	Water (W)	Plasticizer (P)	Aggregate (A)	
					Coarse (Gravel)	Fine (Sand)
	kg/m ³					
OC	400.0	0.0	193.0	1.6	935.0	915.0
FA ₅	380.0	20.0	193.0	1.6	935.0	915.0
FA ₁₀	360.0	40.0	193.0	1.6	935.0	915.0

Table- 5 Proportion of materials in schemes OC, FA₅, and FA₁₀

Scheme	W/C	W/Binder	S/C	S/Binder	A/C	A/Binder
OC	0.48	0.48	2.29	2.29	4.62	4.62
FA ₅	0.51	0.48	2.41	2.29	4.87	4.62
FA ₁₀	0.54	0.48	2.54	2.29	5.14	4.62

During this phase, only cement is being used as the adhesive. However, we will incorporate SFAP and cement in the following two phases. The respective ratios of SFAP added in the two phases are 5% and 10%, which will replace a portion of the cement used.

3.1.2 Stage of Conducting a Concrete Mixing Design

To create the perfect concrete mix, we follow a specific process. First, we combine dry sand and gravel and mix for 2 minutes in a concrete mixer. In the next step, we add the plasticizer in 90~95% of the total water and add it to the mixture while mixing. When all the cement materials are completely mixed, and the mortar has reached the desired consistency, we pour it into cylindrical molds. We placed the cylindrical molds on the vibrating table and continued vibrating until the cement slurry was formed on the surface (approximately one minute). After performing the above steps, after reducing the amount of water on the surface of the sample and losing the glossy state, we smooth its surface using a spatula and place the mold in the laboratory environment, away from heat and direct wind, and for preserving the moisture of the sample in the early hours of its capture, we cover it with a plastic cover and prevent its sudden moisture evaporation. After the concrete mixing process, the slump of concrete is measured in some designs.

3.2 Samples Curing

According to ASTM C511, AASHTO T 23/T 23M-15 Moist Curing Rooms & Water Storage Tanks for Curing specimens were maintained in a curing tank under standard conditions at a temperature of 23 ± 1 °C in saturated lime water until the time of testing at the ages of 28 days the specimens were maintained and processed to obtain the results of these tests, and their comparison is presented subsequently. During the testing procedure, the specimens were subjected to standard curing conditions and tested following the (S.S.D) specifications [12,13].

5. Methods

To ensure accurate compression testing of concrete cylinders, it's essential to evenly distribute the forces applied and ensure that the compressive loads are genuinely axial. Concrete cylinder end grinders provide a direct solution for achieving square ends, and they are suitable for any design strength. They are particularly preferred for concrete mixes with strengths exceeding 7,000psi (48.3MPa). This method is most cost-effective for laboratories with large volumes of higher-strength cylinders to test. As per ASTM C617 / AASHTO T 231, cylindrical concrete samples were ground with a double-sided diamond grinding machine before being tested directly under the compressive strength testing machine [14,15].

Figure- 5 Steps of smoothing the surface of concrete samples by grinding

5.2 Unconfined Compressive Strength Test

According to the ASTM C39 standard, the uniaxial compressive strength was tested at an estimated load that must be applied to the specimen at 0.25 ± 0.05 MPa/s [35 ± 7 psi/s]. The UCS value for each mixture type was obtained by averaging two UCS tests. These tests were conducted after 28 days of curing [16]. (Figure 6)

Figure- 6 Cylindrical sample axial Compressive Strength test- SANTAM, STM-250 (25ton)

6. Result and Discussions

6.1 SFAP classification and XRF test results

SFAP, due to its high levels of silica, alumina, and iron oxide, but low levels of calcium oxide, is classified as F-class fly ash. The XRF analysis test is presented in Table 6.

Table- 6 SFAP XRF analysis

Test Parameters	Unit	Test Result (SFAP)	Scheme	SFAP
SiO ₂	%	88.15	FA ₁₀₋₀₁	293.54
Al ₂ O ₃	%	4.24	FA ₁₀₋₀₁	14.12
CaO	%	1.82	FA ₁₀₋₀₁	6.06
Fe ₂ O ₃	%	1.60	FA ₁₀₋₀₁	5.33
Na ₂ O	%	0.08	FA ₁₀₋₀₁	0.27
MgO	%	0.18	FA ₁₀₋₀₁	0.60
K ₂ O	%	0.51	FA ₁₀₋₀₁	1.70
SO ₃	%	0.02	FA ₁₀₋₀₁	0.67
TiO ₂	%	0.04	FA ₁₀₋₀₁	0.13
L.O. I	%	3.23	FA ₁₀₋₀₁	10.76

6.2 Unified Compressive Strength Test

According to the ASTM C39 compressive strength of samples from mixing designs OC, FA5, and FA10 has been presented and examined at 28 days of age [16]. These designs' compressive strength test results are compared and shown in (Figure-7).

Figure- 7 28-day cylindrical concrete compressive strength with different contents of SPAP

Table- 7 Strength characteristics of samples

Sample ID	Elasticity Modulus		$f'c$
	Initial	Secant	
Unit	Gpa.		Mpa.
OC	28.84	18.83	37.65
FA ₅	33.18	24.92	49.84
FA ₁₀	34.14	26.39	52.78

The graph shows that as the strain increases, the stress initially increases until it reaches a peak and then decreases. The peak represents the maximum compressive strength of the concrete at a given strain level before failure or significant deformation occurs.

- Ordinary concrete has the lowest peak stress at approximately 37 MPa, occurring at a strain just above 0.001.
- Concrete with 5% FA has a higher peak stress of around 49 MPa, which occurs at a strain close to 0.002.
- Concrete with 10% FA shows the highest peak stress at around 52 MPa, which also occurs at a strain close to 0.002.

The inclusion of fly ash (FA) as a partial replacement in concrete mixtures seems to have a positive effect on the compressive strength of the concrete, with higher percentages of FA resulting in higher peak strengths. Moreover, the peak strength is reached at a slightly higher strain for the concrete mixtures with FA compared to ordinary concrete, indicating that they might be slightly more ductile.

7. Determining Density and Aggregate Water Absorption Test

To determine the absorptive water of aggregate materials to meet the requirements of ACI 211 recommendations for preparing a sample under saturated surface dry (S.S.D) conditions and also for volume determination of the absolute volume of concrete (1m³) [17].

(Shown in Table 8,9).

Table- 8 Coarse aggregate determining density and water absorption

Title	Symbol	Unit	Formula	Amount
Dry weight of samples in an oven	A	(gr)		1838.00
Weight of the S.S.D sample	B	(gr)		1853.50
Weight of sample saturated in water	C	(gr)		1176.70
Density of real volume	D_d	(gr/cm ³)	A / (B-C)	2.715
Density of the S.S.D volume	D_s	(gr/cm ³)	B / (B-C)	2.740
Density of the apparent volume	D_a	(gr/cm ³)	A / (A-C)	2.779
Water absorption percentage	ω	(%)	(B-A) / (A×100)	0.843

Table- 9 Fine aggregate determining density and water absorption

Title	Symbol	Unit	Formula	Amount
A dry weight of samples in an oven	A	(gr)		404.0
Weight of the S.S.D volume	S	(gr)		410.2
Weight of (Pycnometer + Water)	B	(gr)		1370.0
Weight of (Pycnometer + Sample + Water)	C	(gr)		1616.5
Density of real volume	D_d	(gr/cm ³)	A / (B+S-C)	2.47
Density of the S.S.D volume	D_s	(gr/cm ³)	S / (B+S-C)	2.51
Density of the apparent volume	D_a	(gr/cm ³)	A / (B+A-C)	2.779
Water absorption percentage	ω	(%)	(S-A) / (A×100)	0.843

The purpose of Tables 5, and 6 is to obtain the specific gravity (G_a) for calculating the unit weight of concrete using a computational method. These tables provide values for determining the specific gravity of aggregate materials through laboratory testing based on the weight of the materials in dry conditions and their buoyancy in water. With the specific gravity (G_a) known, the unit weight of concrete can be calculated using relevant computational equations. In the computational method, we first calculate the unit weight of concrete, and based on this calculation, we proceed with the design. To calculate the absolute volume or actual volume of concrete (Scheme OC), you can use the following equations:

$$V_{abc} = \frac{W}{\rho}$$

Here's:

V_{abs}: represents the absolute volume of concrete.

WW: is the weight of the concrete mix in dry condition (including the weight of aggregate materials, and additives like water and cement).

ρ: denotes the density of concrete.

Here's:

- 400 kg of cement.
- Density of cement (usually around 3150 kg/m³).
- Calculate the absolute volume of cement: $V_{Cement} = \frac{400}{3150} \rightarrow V_{Cement} = 0.12698 \text{ m}^3$
- Convert absolute volume to volume: $Volume_{Cement} = V_{Cement} \times \frac{1}{1000} \text{ m}^3$

Table- 10 Calculating the volume of materials for the Scheme OC absolute volume (1m³)

$V_W = W_w/\rho_w$	→	$V_W = 0.19300 \text{ m}^3$
$V_C = W_c/\rho_c$	→	$V_C = 0.12698 \text{ m}^3$
$V_{Ca} = W_{Ca}/\rho_{Ca}$	→	$V_{Ca} = 0.34124 \text{ m}^3$
$V_{Fa} = W_{Fa}/\rho_{Fa}$	→	$V_{Fa} = 0.36454 \text{ m}^3$
$V_{Pa} = W_{Pa}/\rho_{Pa}$	→	$V_{Pa} = 0.19300 \text{ m}^3$

Here's:

W: water

Ca: Coarse aggregate

Fa: Fine aggregate

Pa: Plasticizer

The real density of aggregate materials is used to calculate the unit weight of concrete

according to the following equation:

$$U = \left[10G_a \times (100 - A) + W_c \times \left(1 - \frac{G_a}{G_s} \right) - W_w \times (G_a - 1) \right]$$

Here's:

U: Fresh concrete specific gravity (kg/m³)

G_a: Average density of fine and coarse aggregate particles (g/cm³)

W_c: (≈3.15 g/cm³)

G_s: Concrete density (kg/m³)

A: Air percentage of fresh concrete

W_w: Water density (kg/m³)

8. Conclusions

During the experiments conducted in the present research aimed at evaluating and comparing concrete without SFAP and concrete containing fly ash with substitution rates of 5 and 10% of the weight of cement used, the following results were obtained:

- The efficiency of concrete increased, and a direct correlation was observed with the amounts of 5% and 10% SFAP used as a partial replacement for cement. In this study, the slump value for concrete increased to 111 mm when 5% SFAP was used as a substitute, and to 222 mm when 10% of the weight of cement was replaced with fly ash.
- It should be noted that the water content for schemes OC, FA₅, and FA₁₀ was kept constant.
- With the use of 5% SFAP as a partial replacement for cement, compressive strength at 28 days increased by 32%.
- With the use of 10% SFAP as a partial replacement for cement, compressive strength at 28 days increased by 40%.
- Based on the stress control axial strain curve obtained during uniaxial compression testing of concrete specimens and the reported curves in the present research, it can be concluded that during the increase in compressive strength, the concrete exhibits desirable residual compressive strength at the yielding and ultimate stages, and its brittleness has been effectively reduced.
- Following the results obtained from the present research, the assessment of concrete's modulus of elasticity becomes a priority for researchers involved in this research project and other related studies. Therefore, it is recommended that other researchers, professors, students, and engineers conduct further research and investigation in this area.

"In future research, it is advisable for scholars, students, and researchers in the field of civil engineering to expand the range of fly ash (FA) percentages analyzed. This will provide a more comprehensive understanding of how FA content affects the mechanical properties of concrete."

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